

Research Software Engineering in the NFDI (INFRA-WG-RSE)

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Research Software Engineering in NFDI?

NFDI Mission: Research data are systematically accessed, networked and made usable in a sustainable and qualitative manner for the entire German science system.

INFRA-WG-RSE: The working group connects the NFDI consortia in software-related aspects. It focuses on three key areas: research software, software communities, and the software infrastructure of the NFDI. In an advisory and supportive role, the working group operates a central forum and establishes the necessary software ecosystem within the NFDI for the professional development of software infrastructure components, which collectively form an integral part of the NFDI. Additionally, the working group serves as an interface between the NFDI and comparable European and international initiatives to enhance the interoperability of the NFDI with other infrastructures. *Goal:* Brings the NFDI consortia together in all software-related aspects. *Working mode:* Small subgroups work on individual tasks, monthly WG-wide coordination meetings.

Focal Points: Infrastructure, Research Software, RSEs
Objectives: Ecosystem, Forum, Expert Panel, Marketplace, Use Cases, Best Practices & Training
Interfaces: to other measures and RSE groups and chapters

Task "Jupyter Services" (Jupyter4NFDI)

- Bring together the **JupyterHub providers** in Germany
- Collect and **list available hubs** at a common web site
- **Jupyter4NFDI**, a central JupyterHub, supported by NFDI Section Common Infrastructures; Phase: Initialisation

Task "Software Marketplace" (nfdi.software)

- Allow **accessing the portfolio** of research software in the **NFDI**
- **central marketplace** to improve **access to research software**
- **nfdi.software**, Software Marketplace, supported by NFDI Section Common Infrastructures; Phase: Initialisation

Further Tasks

- Training Materials:** Create recommendations to spread good practices using available content.
- Mission Statement:** Develop a common mission statement "Software Engineering in the NFDI".
- Status Quo Survey and Report:** Apply a RSE survey for a "Landscape Analysis" within the NFDI.
- Overarching Initiatives:** Ensure connectivity and compatibility with European and international efforts.
- Software Ecosystem:** Develop a draft strategy for establishing a software ecosystem within the NFDI.
- Use Cases:** Identify use cases for a cross-consortium, prototypical development of the software ecosystem.
- Quality Criteria for Research Software:** Identify and develop suitable, in particular easy-to-record, indicators.
- Criteria for NFDI Components:** Ensure reliability, compatibility and security; provide checklists / test suite.

Arbeitskreis NFDI within deRSE e.V.

The **Arbeitskreis NFDI** within **deRSE e.V.** creates the **hub** for NFDI related RSEs within the **distributed NFDI consortia**.

How to improve the visibility and added value of RSE(s) in NFDI?

Join our Meet-Up and fill out our **survey** on **RSE(s) activities**.

